

European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition

Work Package WP6

NA5 - Management and Organization of RI Access Activities

Deliverable D6.1

D-NA5.1 Specification of the Trans-national Access and Virtual Access Programmes

Funding Instrument: Research and Innovation Action
Call: H2020-INFRAIA-2019-1
Call Topic: INFRAIA-01-2018-2019 Integrating Activities for Advanced Communities

Project Start: 1 April 2020
Project Duration: 54 months

Beneficiary in Charge: Fundación TECNALIA Research & Innovation (TEC)

Document Identifier: doi:[10.5281/zenodo.4450833](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4450833)

Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	✓
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Deliverable Information

Document Administrative Information	
Project Acronym:	ERIGrid 2.0
Project Number:	870620
Deliverable Number:	D6.1
Deliverable Full Title:	D-NA5.1 Specification of the Trans-national Access and Virtual Access Programmes
Deliverable Short Title:	Specification of Access Programmes
Document Identifier:	ERIGrid2-D61-SpecificationOfAccessProgrammes-submitted
Beneficiary in Charge:	Fundación TECNALIA Research & Innovation (TEC)
Report Version:	v1.7
Contractual Date:	30/09/2020
Report Submission Date:	29/04/2021
Dissemination Level:	PU
Nature:	Report
Lead Author(s):	J.E. Rodríguez (TEC)
Co-author(s):	S. Vogel (RWTH), T. Strasser (AIT)
Keywords:	Lab Access, Trans-national Access, Virtual Access, Remote Access
Status:	_ draft, _ final, <u> x </u> submitted

Change Log

Date	Version	Author/Editor	Summary of Changes Made
10/06/2020	v1.0	T. Strasser (AIT)	Initial document structure
05/10/2020	v1.1	J.E. Rodríguez (TEC)	Refinement of document structure, first inputs
05/01/2021	v1.2	S. Vogel (RWTH)	Specification of Virtual Access Programme
15/01/2021	v1.3	J.E. Rodríguez (TEC)	Specification of Lab Access Programme; inclusion of supporting documents as appendices.
09/04/2021	v1.4	M. Calin (AIT), K. Anastasakis (HEDNO)	Internal review and modification based on the review.
29/03/2021	v1.5	J.E. Rodríguez (TEC)	Reviewers' comments implemented
28/04/2021	v1.6	E. Mrakotsky (AIT)	Language and grammar check
29/04/2021	v1.7	T. Strasser (AIT)	Final version

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	6
1. Introduction	7
1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document	7
1.2 Structure of the Document	8
2. Eligibility of the Lab Access User Groups	9
3. Lab Access Procedure	10
3.1 STEP 1: Publications of the Calls for Proposals	10
3.2 STEP 2: Submission of the User Proposals	11
3.3 STEP 3: Evaluation of the User Proposals	12
3.4 STEP 4: Proposal Selection and Notification to the User Group	13
3.5 STEP 5: Access to the Lab	14
3.6 STEP 6: Reporting and Dissemination of the Project Results	15
4. Reimbursement of the Lab Access Expenses	18
5. Remote Lab Access Possibilities	19
6. Virtual Access Services	20
6.1 General Virtual Access Procedure	20
6.2 Virtual Access Facilities	22
6.3 User Support Forum	26
6.4 User Questionnaire	27
6.5 Single-sign on System	27
6.6 Access Metrics and Statistics	28
7. Conclusions	29
References	30
Appendix A: Proposal Template	31
Appendix B: Contract Model	35
Appendix C: EC Questionnaire	52
Appendix D: Expenses Declaration Form	53

List of Figures

Figure 1: Lab access call reference timeline.	10
Figure 2: Sequence of lab access calls.....	11
Figure 3: Overview of the VA user flow.	21
Figure 4: Overview of the provided VA facilities.	22
Figure 5: Screenshot of RSE's DER-TF DAAS.	23
Figure 6: Screenshot of the ICCS Virtual Lab.....	23
Figure 7: Screenshot of ICCS' OpenAFPM.....	24
Figure 8: Screenshot of AIT's SmartEST Sim Lab.....	24
Figure 9: Screenshot of RWTH's Vlab.	25
Figure 10: Screenshot of the VA support forum.....	27
Figure 11: Screenshot of the VA questionnaire.	28

List of Abbreviations

AFPM	Axial Flux Permanent Magnet
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FEMM	Finite Element Method Magnetics
GUI	Graphic User Interface
H2020	European Commission Framework Programme Horizon 2020
HTD	Holistic Test Description
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IdP	Identity Provider
IP	Intellectual Property
P2X	Power to Gas, Power to Heat, etc.
PMU	Phasor Measurement Unit
RI	Research Infrastructure
RP	Responsible Person
RTD	Research and Technological Development
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
TSDB	Time Series Database
UG	User Group
USP	User Selection Panel
VA	Virtual Access

Executive Summary

In a similar way to its predecessor ERIGrid, the fundamental objective of the ERIGrid 2.0 project is to provide on-site and remote lab access to an integrated Research Infrastructure (RI), operated at 21 distributed installations in 13 countries. The ERIGrid 2.0 lab access programme is offered mainly to the European research community where the need of investigating and validating complex smart grids configurations and smart energy systems is essential. The access scheme includes free of charge access to the integrated infrastructure, technological and scientific support and funding to cover travel and accommodation during the on-site stays.

This document specifies the general rules and conditions of the ERIGrid 2.0 lab access scheme, describing the eligibility of the User Groups (UGs), access procedure, public calls, proposal evaluation and selection, and hosting of researcher groups at the facilities on offer. For the user projects to be implemented in the lab, a contract must be signed between the user group and the host laboratory before getting access to the infrastructure: a contract model is also included in this report which is to be used as a reference for regulating the implementation of all projects and stays at ERIGrid 2.0 infrastructures. Moreover, this document indicates the mandatory provisions for the dissemination of the results of the implemented user projects.

At the difference of ERIGrid, ERIGrid 2.0 widens the scope of accessibility offering the possibility of Virtual Access (VA) to researchers around the world. Eight databases, real-time data or simulation platforms are made available on-line free of charge, without prior submission and evaluation of a project proposal, the signature of a contract or a mandatory reporting of the results.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

The ERIGrid project paved the way for mitigating the lack of validation schemes for smart grid configurations, based on a holistic and cyber-physical approach. Based on the results from the predecessor project, ERIGrid 2.0 expands the research services and tools of the RI for validating smart energy networks with the electric power grid as the main backbone.

ERIGrid 2.0 is a pan-European RI, which integrates 21 first-class laboratories located in 13 European countries, and aims at placing this RI at the disposal of the European research community, including industrial organisations, in a four-year access programme supported by the European Commission (EC) through the European Commission Framework Programme Horizon 2020 (H2020).

ERIGrid 2.0 offers to all interested researchers in the domains of smart grids and smart energy systems free of charge access to RIs and associated services along with logistical, technological and scientific support for their own experimental research. Access to physical laboratories can be organised either on-site or remotely. In addition to the lab operation costs, the on-site lab access scheme also covers the expenses of travelling and accommodation for the stays¹ at the selected laboratories.

In order to become a beneficiary of this opportunity, the user group must submit a proposal that will be evaluated by an independent User Selection Panel (USP). Once the proposal is approved by the USP and the work programme agreed between the user group and the host lab, a contract must be signed for regulating the access, use conditions and responsibilities of all parties involved. When the access is completed, in accordance with the access contract and the EC conditions, the user group must submit a technical report on the experiment implementation and results, which will be made publicly available through the project website.

This deliverable does not include the descriptions of the laboratories offered by ERIGrid 2.0 and the concrete access conditions applicable to the individual installations. This information is available on the ERIGrid 2.0 website².

Furthermore, ERIGrid 2.0 provides to researchers world-wide the opportunity to access research infrastructures virtually. VA is made available free of charge, to openly available resources such as databases, real-time data or simulation platforms (currently, eight on-line facilities and services are offered). VA aims at facilitating casual access with minimal administrative overheads compared to the more elaborate application and selection process defined for the on-site or remote lab access procedure (i.e., in the VA there is no need for submission and evaluation of any project proposal, signature of a contract or the mandatory reporting of the experiment results).

The objective of this deliverable is to be a self-contained document used as a reference for consultation on the instructions and conditions for the access to physical labs (on-site and remotely) and virtual services. The document specifies the general rules of the ERIGrid 2.0 lab access and VA schemes, covering the eligibility of the users, the end-to-end procedure to be followed in the lab access programme (call schedule, proposal submission, evaluation and selection, contractual conditions for the access, mandatory reporting of the user project results, etc.), and the VA mechanisms.

¹For some international users there could be limitations; for further details see Section 2 of this document.

²<https://erigrd2.eu/>

As a fundamental part of this deliverable, a contract model is also provided as an appendix for regulating the critical aspects of the users' stay in the ERIGrid 2.0 infrastructures. The contract must be signed before the commencement of the project implementation between the host lab and the user group. The contract model is a basic reference, thus extensions or specific modifications may need to be introduced by each host lab as necessary to cover country regulations, legal constraints or company policies.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 2 focuses on the eligibility conditions to be fulfilled by the users of the lab access programme; Section 3 describes the step-by-step lab access procedure; Section 4 deals with the basic scheme of the reimbursement of the lab access expenses to the users; Section 5 points out the remote lab access possibility, and finally, Section 6 focuses on the VA services and mechanisms.

For the sake of clarity, the following associated templates are also included within the appendices of this document: Appendix A: Proposal Template, Appendix B: Contract Model (as a basic reference for UG projects), Appendix C: EC Questionnaire, and Appendix D: Expenses Declaration Form.

Further information on the ERIGrid 2.0 project, the detailed technical descriptions of the offered RIs (for lab access), and the services/tools (for VA) are available at the website³.

³<https://erigrd2.eu>

2 Eligibility of the Lab Access User Groups

Lab access is provided to selected 'Users' and 'User groups' (UG) (teams of one or more researchers led by a user group leader). The selection will be done through the evaluation of the received user project proposals by an independent review panel of experts from different domains that are involved in smart grids and smart energy systems (power systems, Information and Communications Technology (ICT), cybersecurity, etc.).

The user group leader and the majority of the user group members should work in an institution/Small and Medium-sized Enterprise (SME) located in a country different to the country where the lab is located ('trans-national' characteristic of the lab access). For multi-site projects this rule applies to all sites to be accessed.

The ERIGrid 2.0 lab access is open to engineers and researchers that are primarily from organisations (this includes SMEs and larger industries) located in a European Union (EU) Member State or H2020 Associated Countries⁴ (Albania, Armenia, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Faroe Islands, Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia, Georgia, Iceland, Israel, Moldova, Montenegro, Norway, Serbia, Switzerland, Tunisia, Turkey, and Ukraine).

Limited lab access is also available to applicants from non-EU countries ('third countries')⁵: the limitation is not on the number of UG from these countries but on the amount of access that can be provided by ERIGrid 2.0; access for UG with a majority of users working in third countries is limited to 20% of the total amount of units of access provided under the grant. The general H2020 conditions for international cooperation and corresponding rules apply for formal eligibility.

Only UG that agree to disseminate the results that they have generated under the project are eligible to benefit from free of charge access to the infrastructure. This mandatory dissemination requirement does not apply to SMEs. Young scientists at the start of their careers as well as female researchers will be positively considered.

On average, the duration of the stay at a RI will be 1-4 weeks, but in some cases longer stays of up to three months may also be justified (for visits to the installation/s exceeding three months, written approval from the EC must be requested by the access provider).

Despite the fact that the user group implementing the project in the lab is normally composed of two or three researchers, one single researcher is also allowed. Unless fully justified, the maximum number of researchers getting access to the lab must not be more than three.

⁴https://ec.europa.eu/info/files/countries-associated-horizon-2020-framework-programme_en

⁵https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/wp/2018-2020/annexes/h2020-wp1820-annex-a-countries-rules_en.pdf

3 Lab Access Procedure

This section describes the steps of the entire procedure, detailing how the lab access in ERIGrid 2.0 will be implemented through successive public calls. It provides the criteria for the assessment and selection of proposals by the USP and sets the general rules for the development of the selected user projects as well as the dissemination of the results. In addition, it defines the general contractual conditions pertaining to the researcher's stay at the infrastructures. Further elaboration and specifics will be detailed in the corresponding contract (see also Appendix B: Contract Model).

The general timeline is shown in Figure 1. As a reference, the duration of the call and the associated user access will last for around twelve months, with the following schedule:

- Every call will remain open for three months.
- The received proposals will be normally evaluated within one month (two months maximum) after the closing date of each call.
- The access period must be allocated within six months after acceptance of the proposal with a typical duration of 1-4 weeks (and limited to a maximum of three months, if well justified). The implementation can be split into two phases (two access periods) in the lab, if necessary, but not more.
- After finishing the lab access, there is a two month time-limit for the user group to carry out the mandatory reporting of the project experiments.

Figure 1: Lab access call reference timeline.

In ERIGrid 2.0, the lab access calls will be launched every four months, with the same reference timeline as outlined in Figure 1. The call sequence for the first three calls is illustrated in Figure 2.

3.1 STEP 1: Publications of the Calls for Proposals

ERIGrid 2.0 will launch every four months a call for proposals for lab access to conduct experiments at the involved RIs (see their descriptions at the ERIGrid 2.0 lab access page⁶). Overall, a total of ten calls are foreseen during the course of ERIGrid 2.0.

The announcement of the lab access calls will emerge through the ERIGrid 2.0 website⁷, social networks, advertisement through different channels (posters, flyers, press releases, ERIGrid 2.0 partners' web pages, etc.), publications at conferences, workshops and journals, and through direct contact with potential users.

⁶<https://erigid2.eu/lab-access/>

⁷<https://erigid2.eu/>

Figure 2: Sequence of lab access calls.

3.1.1 Topics Targeted by the Calls

The calls for proposals are targeted to research and development of smart grid and smart energy system concepts and configurations, and to testing and validation methods and tools following a holistic approach.

Future electrical networks will integrate higher shares of fluctuating renewable energy, distributed energy resources at all voltage levels, active prosumers, electrical vehicles, demand side management programmes, etc. Besides the power system components, like the grid infrastructure, storage, generation, consumption, etc., the future energy ecosystem also comprises ICT, cybersecurity, sector coupling, multi-domain topics (heat, Power to Gas, Power to Heat, etc. (P2X)), markets, regulation, etc. Any project proposal covering this broad and complex scope of topics will fall into the ERIGrid 2.0 lab access scope and may be eligible.

In this context, those proposals that are clearly contributing to the improvement of the services provided by the infrastructures, the harmonisation and optimisation of methodologies, and the reinforcement of the partnership with the industry will receive a special consideration.

The experimental research on the selected research topics must be implemented in one (or several) of the offered labs listed at the project website. Therefore, the technical and economical feasibility will be checked in advance by the corresponding labs based on the available equipment/facility and offered services.

3.2 STEP 2: Submission of the User Proposals

In response to the calls, UGs will submit their project proposals to ERIGrid 2.0. The submission will take place electronically before the call deadline on the project website (via *ConfTool*⁸). The proposal document must be completed using the proposal template (see Appendix A: Proposal Template), available on the project website.

The UG preparing the proposal will indicate the preferred infrastructures (one, two or three options are allowed) where the experimental research will be carried out. These preferences will be considered, to the extent possible, during the evaluation process.

⁸<https://conftool.net/erigrd2/>

Normally (it is not mandatory but recommended for a successful proposal), before submission of the application form, the user group will contact the preferred infrastructure/s to check the preliminary availability of the facilities and feasibility of the experiments, and to clarify the research objectives and access conditions. However, this consultation will never mean any preference or special treatment of the proposal during the independent evaluation process.

Depending on the objectives and needs, an individual project could be implemented in several laboratories ('multi-site user project'). In this case, the user will justify the need of getting access to several installations in the proposal and indicate the selected ones. The user will have to clearly establish the work programme, specifying the sequence of the lab accesses and expected duration at the different installations.

3.3 STEP 3: Evaluation of the User Proposals

The selection of researchers or research teams benefitting from the access opportunity will be carried out through an independent peer-review evaluation of their research projects.

The evaluation of the user project proposals will be done by the USP. The entire evaluation process is expected to be completed within 1-2 months after the deadline for the submission of proposals in each call. In parallel with the USP evaluation, the laboratories selected by the user group in the proposal will perform a so-called 'pre-screening'.

3.3.1 Proposal Pre-screening

The pre-screening is the first assessment of the technical, economic and organisational feasibility of the received proposal done by the three labs selected (preferred) by the user group. Technical problems, risks and related costs will be considered. No further evaluation criteria will be employed at this stage.

If the proposal is not feasible at any of the three selected labs, it will be circulated among the rest of the labs so they can assess it in terms of feasibility. The proposal will be assigned to one of the labs not initially selected by the UG, but able to implement the user project. If more than one infrastructure can develop the project, the UG will be contacted to choose. Finally, if the proposal (even modified or adapted) cannot be technically implemented at any lab, it will be rejected as unfeasible.

The pre-screening is expected to run smoothly once the preliminary contact has been established between the proposing user group and the selected infrastructures.

3.3.2 Proposal Evaluation by the User Selection Panel

All received proposals will be evaluated by the USP following the principles of transparency, fairness and impartiality. The USP is a group of experts from within and outside ERIGrid 2.0 partner organisations with diverse profiles (academia, research, industry), covering the different domains of the smart grids and smart energy systems arena (power systems, ICT, etc.). Each proposal will be assessed by at least three experts of the USP. The ERIGrid 2.0 Lab Access Manager and the ERIGrid 2.0 Coordinator will not participate in the proposal evaluation but shall guarantee the compliance of the proposal with the eligibility rules of the lab access.

Each USP member reviewing a proposal will evaluate according to the following categories:

1. *General quality of the proposal* (score: 0-10): completeness and organisation of the proposal, clear definition of the objectives and expected results, relevance of the proposed dissemination actions, justified amount of access requested.
2. *Scientific/technical merit* (score: 0-10): scientific and technical relevance, originality and innovation, methodology, robust and realistic test/evaluation approach.
3. *Improve know-how and capacity of the lab* (score: 0-10): improvement of know-how within the laboratories, enhancement of lab technologies and methods, alignment with ERIGrid 2.0 scenarios/use cases/test cases, synergies with other projects and cooperation with other infrastructures.
4. *Compliance with EU policies and priorities* (score: 0-10): compliance with European Research and Technological Development (RTD) policies and priorities, social impact, impact on EU industry (e.g., standardisation and competitiveness), and sustainable growth interest. Further, special consideration and priority should be attributed to new users that have not previously used the installation, users working in countries where no equivalent research infrastructure exists, young researchers, and of course to female researchers.

Additionally, in this phase the USP may provide comments and suggestions to improve the project implementation in the lab (if the proposal is accepted in the end) or to build a better proposal for resubmission to future calls (if the proposal is rejected in the current call).

For each proposal, the USP expert will issue a score, which will be the sum of the above four individual scores per category. All the categories have the same weight. The final score of the proposal will be calculated as the mean value of the scores issued by the USP members evaluating the proposal, expressed in % over the maximum of 40 points:

- Excellent (75-100%)
- Good (50-75%)
- Fair (25-50%)
- Poor (0-25%)

In addition, during the USP evaluation all proposals are also checked against plagiarism (in accordance to the general H2020 strategy⁹). Proposals with an unjustified high amount of similarity will not be considered for realisation, but will be rejected.

3.4 STEP 4: Proposal Selection and Notification to the User Group

All the proposals will be ranked based on the scores assigned by the USP. 'Poor'-scored proposals will normally be rejected. Proposals resubmitted, that may have been unsuccessful in previous calls, will be evaluated as new ones.

The User Group (UG) of each proposal will be formally notified of the evaluation result at the end of the evaluation period (1-2 months after the call deadline). This result will be accompanied with comments and suggestions for possible improvements.

If due to technical/economic/organisational feasibility or laboratory availability none of the labs selected by the user group can be allocated, a different lab may be offered. If this is the case, the UG can (1) withdraw the proposal, (2) update and resubmit the proposal as a new one in

⁹https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/checks-audits-reviews-investigations_en.htm

one of the next calls, (3) remain with the assigned score for the next call, when it will be ranked in a new list with the new proposals, or (4) accept the alternative lab suggested by the lab access organisers.

3.5 STEP 5: Access to the Lab

When a proposal is accepted, a focused interaction between the proposing user group and the host infrastructure starts. The estimated access period indicated in the proposal must be confirmed and agreed between the user group and the host lab. Normally, the access period should be allocated to a date within the next six months after the acceptance notification to the user, following the agreement of the technical details for executing the experiments and fulfilment of administrative issues.

3.5.1 Signature of the Contract

Before the commencement of the project, a contract must be signed between the host lab and the user group (individual contracts with each host lab involved will be necessary for a 'multi-site project'). A basic template contract is provided for use in all ERIGrid 2.0 lab access projects as a reference model, but extensions or specific modifications may be introduced by each of the labs for the project, as necessary. This contract model is included in Appendix B: Contract Model. The contract includes the clear identification of UG members that are authorised to enter the infrastructure, the responsible person at the host lab that will act as the single point of contact for the user group during the project, basic conditions regarding confidentiality, liability, intellectual property rights and safety, all of which must be agreed upon well in advance. Reporting of project results by the users is key for the EC and therefore becomes binding by means of this contract. Finally, the conditions and procedure for reimbursement of expenses are included as well.

Additionally, the contract includes an initial stay duration for the access period, to be agreed upon by the UG and the host lab. However, the stay duration can change during the course of the project due to several factors. At the end of the stay, both the UG and the host lab must sign a declaration covering the final and definitive use of the infrastructure.

Finally, the contract has a Technical Annex that formulates the Test Case and describes the work programme (tasks, experiment plan, time schedule, etc.) to be performed during the access period in the lab. This annex must be coherent with the proposal (even though some adjustments in practice are allowed). Significant modifications of the technical content or the access conditions (e.g., number of access days) with respect to the planned ones in the proposal, should be checked with the ERIGrid 2.0 lab access organisers.

For the formulation of the Test Case in the Technical Annex of the contract, the use of the Holistic Test Description (HTD) canvas is mandatory. HTD is a methodology developed in the ERIGrid project that facilitates the conception, deconstruction and reproduction of complex experimental designs in the domains of cyber-physical energy systems (Heussen et al., 2019). The complete HTD method comprises several sequential steps on the path to implementation of an experiment (*Test Case, Qualification Strategy, Test Specification, Experiment Realisation Plan and Experiment Specification*), however, only the initial one (*Test Case* formulation) is required for the contract.

3.5.2 Assistance to the User Group

Each lab must nominate a Responsible Person (RP) for each accepted user project (linked to a proposal). The RP is in charge of supervising the experimental activity at the lab (including the safety matters), and supporting the UG in all technical, administrative and logistic needs. The RP is also the reference person for reporting to ERIGrid 2.0 on the state of the activity running at the lab.

3.5.3 Declaration of Use of the Lab

At the end of the access in the lab, the UG must declare the use of the installations by signing a specific form (attached to the contract) and indicating the total number of 'access days' (days of real use of the lab) and the total number of 'stay days' (which includes the access days in the lab but normally also the days working in the office of the host, weekend days if applicable, etc.) of each member of the UG.

3.6 STEP 6: Reporting and Dissemination of the Project Results

As soon as the experiments on the infrastructure come to an end, the UG must fulfil the reporting and dissemination commitments, specified in the access contract. Two mandatory reporting actions must be accomplished by the UG within two months after the end of the access; i.e., an on-line questionnaire for the EC along with the project technical report.

3.6.1 User Group Questionnaire

One of the aims of the European RI Action is to provide scientists from anywhere within the community with easy access to Europe's major RIs. The Action is implemented through grant agreements between the EC and major European RIs. These grant agreements serve to support, among others, the mobility costs of visiting scientists and their costs of using the infrastructure.

By means of a questionnaire completed by the user group, the EC evaluates the European RI Action in general, and monitors the ERIGrid 2.0 lab access programme in particular. All replies are treated in strictest confidence. The questionnaire to collect the user feedback on the access is included in Appendix C: EC Questionnaire of this document but must be filled on-line at the corresponding EC page¹⁰.

3.6.2 User Project Technical Report

In addition to the general feedback on the access service captured by the EC questionnaire, dissemination of the project results is crucial. The first step in this process is the preparation of the project technical report to provide all the technical details and to put the investigation results at the disposal of the research community.

For some industrial users' projects, the technical report might contain confidential information. In this case, special provisions will be taken by ERIGrid 2.0 and the EC, among them, the

¹⁰<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS>

technical report will not be made publicly available (it will be distributed just to the Host Infrastructure, the ERIGrid 2.0 Project Coordinator, and the EC). SMEs are excluded from the preparation of this report.

A draft version of the technical report must be prepared by the user group and sent to the host infrastructure for comments and validation. After the needed interactions between the UG and the host lab, the definitive technical report will be sent to the ERIGrid 2.0 lab access organisers.

The basic content of the user project technical report is the following:

1. General information of the user project
 - Title,
 - Acronym,
 - Host lab,
 - Access period, and
 - UG members.
2. Executive summary
3. Research motivation, objectives, and scope
4. Brief state-of-the-art or state-of-technology
5. Tests and experiments executed
 - Test plan,
 - Standards, procedures and methodology,
 - Test set-ups and implementation details (involved equipment and communications, control strategy, monitoring aspects, etc.), and
 - Data management and processing.
6. Results and conclusions
7. Open issues and suggestions for improvements

An executive summary of up to two pages also has to be included in this technical report, presenting in a condensed manner the objectives and motivation, the basic project implementation details (approach, methodology, set-up) and the main achievements (results, conclusions and lessons learned). This summary will be widely used in the course of the ERIGrid 2.0 project through its website, dissemination material, general presentations, etc.

3.6.3 Further Publications

In order to provide evidence of the soundness of the scientific work performed at the host lab in ERIGrid 2.0, the UG is encouraged to publish the results in journals, conferences, etc. As soon as they are accepted for publication or published, the UG will provide detailed information to the ERIGrid 2.0 Lab Access Manager and the ERIGrid 2.0 Project Coordinator on the corresponding abstracts, papers, reports, conference presentations, etc. related to the access activity. Preferably, open access publications should be chosen.

Whenever possible, ERIGrid 2.0 would like to receive any publication made as a result of the access to publish it on the website (provided that the full rights of the researchers are not affected and the copyright conditions are not violated; e.g., pre-print or post-print copies could be acceptable for non-open access publications).

Presentations and publications which result from lab access in ERIGrid 2.0 must be in English (at least the first one associated to the access), display the EU emblem and contain the acknowledgement:

'This research has been performed using the ERIGrid 2.0 Research Infrastructure and is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under the Grant Agreement No. 870620. The support of the European Research Infrastructure ERIGrid 2.0 and its partner «name» is very much appreciated'.

Any communication activity related to the project must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the EC is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains ('Disclaimer excluding the EC responsibility').

According to the conditions of the H2020 support for lab access, ERIGrid 2.0 reports to the EC will contain the names, home institutions and description of the work of the users. The ERIGrid 2.0 website will publish a list of projects naming the researchers' organisations, research project titles and short descriptions, as well as the facilities used. Users must also note that the EC has the right to publish the list of users.

4 Reimbursement of the Lab Access Expenses

The lab access offered by ERIGrid 2.0 covers the UGs expenses for travel and subsistence according to the H2020 rules and the host RI conditions¹¹.

Reasonable travel expenses (low-cost flight company, economy class and public transportation, whenever possible) will be reimbursed with the presentation of the corresponding invoices or receipts. For the daily subsistence expenses (accommodation in conventional – not luxury – hotels or equivalent lodging, and meals in regular restaurants), two possibilities (or a combination) are allowed depending on the host lab's conditions:

- *Payment by invoice*: The UG will get the refund of the subsistence costs after the stay, when declaring the incurred expenses and presenting the invoices/receipts (same mechanism as the reimbursement of the travel expenses); normally, the host infrastructure indicates a reference maximum amount per person for the daily subsistence fee as an indication for the users.
- *Daily allowance*: Each user receives a per-day pocket money for each day of stay according to the host infrastructure conditions to pay for all the daily subsistence expenses. The user must sign the corresponding payment receipts provided by the host infrastructure; one for the ERIGrid 2.0 project records, and presumably, another one for the host lab's accounting department.

A template for the declaration of the expenses by the user group can be found in Appendix D: Expenses Declaration Form and must be sent to the host lab for approval and refund. In a similar way, another template will be used as a payment receipt by the host infrastructure when a daily allowance is used.

¹¹<https://erigrd2.eu/lab-access/>

5 Remote Lab Access Possibilities

An alternative to the on-site lab access is the so-called remote lab access. By means of this option, an accepted user project can be implemented in a lab without the presence of the UG in the installation. All the involved experiments will be carried out by the host lab staff in fluent communication (phone, email, etc.) with the user, who will follow the work remotely. In this case, the experiment preparation phase is even more important than in an on-site access, since the users will not be in the lab for direct supervision and set-up adjustments.

This access type has several advantages:

- *Lower access expenses:* No trips, accommodation, insurances, visas for non-EU users, etc. are involved. Declaration of expenses and reimbursement do not apply.
- *Safety issues:* No safety indications and precautions are needed for the users since they will not be physically present in the lab.

However, the laboratory must be booked in advance for these experiments during the access period, and the host lab staff will be preparing the set-ups and performing the testing, with the corresponding costs. A contract between the UG and the host lab is mandatory for this type of access too, since confidentiality, liability and Intellectual Property (IP) issues still apply and must be formalised. Similarly, the mandatory technical report must be submitted by the user when the experiments are finished within the next two months.

6 Virtual Access Services

6.1 General Virtual Access Procedure

The ERIGrid 2.0 project provides the opportunity to access virtual infrastructures to researchers world-wide. With this addition to the first ERIGrid project, the aim is to provide access to virtual data and services needed for research. This access is made available free of charge, to open and freely available resources such as databases, real-time data or simulation platforms. It aims at facilitating casual access with minimal administrative overheads compared to the more elaborate application and selection process defined in the lab access procedure described in previous sections.

With the VA scheme the project focuses on the publication of existing software projects and data sets under open access/source licenses to a broader audience. Nonetheless, the VA program seeks to supply VA access providers with the needed feedback to improve their services. Moreover, as the kick-off of the ERIGrid 2.0 project coincided with the global Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, VA offers a viable alternative to physical lab access as world-wide travel is heavily restricted. At the same time, VA is capable of reaching out and attracting new users for upcoming lab access calls.

The EC defines VA as follows:

VA ensures free of charge access to e-infrastructure, namely to:

- Sophisticated computer services,
- Powerful computers, networks, grids, repositories, databases.
- Safely storing large quantities of scientific data,
- Participation in virtual research communities, and
- World-class operational communication and computing infrastructure to facilitate scientific research.

VA is not the same as remote lab access. Both access opportunities are provided over communication networks. However, only the access to VA facilities is open to all users (i.e., users are not selected based on their research proposals). In the VA modality there is no competitive selection of the users as in the lab access (remote or on-site) procedure through the USP. The remote lab access, on the other hand, follows the same procedure as the on-site lab access and includes individual on-site support from the access provider.

VA may require user identification or not. This can be implemented through a user login system and automated means of user verification (e.g., mail addresses) to avoid the abuse of services. The implementation of user identification depends on the RI policies of the respective access providers.

The access to the VA infrastructures is not measured as it is in the typical lab access (in terms of “access days” spent in the lab). There is no unit of access defined but some access metrics and statistics will be collected.

A typical user workflow is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Overview of the VA user flow.

6.2 Virtual Access Facilities

In ERIGrid 2.0 eight out of the 20 consortium partners offer at least one VA infrastructure. These partners are namely: AIT, DTU, HEDNO, ICCS, OFFIS, RSE, RWTH & UoS. A total of nine VA infrastructures are provided. Only the project partner ICCS provides access to two facilities. Figure 4 provides an overview of the available facilities as listed in the ERIGrid 2.0 lab access page¹².

Figure 4: Overview of the provided VA facilities.

In the following section the key facts of each of the VA facilities are provided.

6.2.1 RSE: DER-TF DAAS

Access Provider: RSE

Details: <https://erigrd2.eu/der-tf-daas/>

Description: RSE's DER-TF DaaS (see Figure 5) is a platform that provides the access to historical and real-time data of a real low voltage microgrid. The infrastructure is composed of a Time Series Database (TSDB) and an object storage (topology, assets, test case description) that is accessible through a web-interface that allows exploration of the information at component and system levels. This infrastructure is cloud oriented with a web application which allows simultaneous use by several users.

6.2.2 ICCS: Virtual Lab

Access Provider: ICCS

Details: <https://erigrd2.eu/virtual-lab/>

Description: The Virtual Lab (see Figure 6) is an online educational simulation tool that mimics the operation of the actual laboratory microgrid of EES lab of ICCS. A mathematical model of the laboratory microgrid has been developed along with a user-friendly Graphic User Interface (GUI). The user can observe several variables (e.g., voltage, active power, reactive power, etc.) and perform several actions (e.g., change the power factor of the

¹²<https://erigrd2.eu/lab-access/>

Figure 5: Screenshot of RSE's DER-TF DAAS.

inverter). The simulation tool includes two different laboratory setups and corresponding experiments: voltage control, and microgrid operation.

Figure 6: Screenshot of the ICCS Virtual Lab.

6.2.3 ICCS: OpenAFPM

Access Provider: ICCS

Details: <https://erigrad2.eu/openafpm/>

Description: The OpenAFM (Online Design Tools for Locally Manufactured Small Wind Turbines, see Figure 7) modelling tools can be used for designing Axial Flux Permanent Magnet (AFPM) generators for wind electric systems with the use of the open source finite element analysis software “Finite Element Method Magnetics (FEMM)”. Developed

Figure 7: Screenshot of ICCS' OpenAFPM.

by ICCS, this tool-set assists designers and practitioners involved with small scale wind electric systems. The tool is also used for educational purposes.

6.2.4 AIT: SmartEST Sim Lab

Access Provider: AIT

Details: <https://erigrid2.eu/smartest-sim-lab/>

Description: AIT's SmartEST Sim Lab (see Figure 8) is a Simulation-as-a-Service platform that is open to the public and can be used free of charge. It provides a web-based co-simulation platform based on mosaik, Docker, JupyterLab and JupyterHub.

Figure 8: Screenshot of AIT's SmartEST Sim Lab.

6.2.5 OFFIS: SESA Virtual Sim

Access Provider: OFFIS

Details: <https://erigrd2.eu/sesa-virtual-sim/>

Description: The core of the SESA Virtual Sim is formed by the co-simulation framework mosaik and a virtualisation server. The server allows the instantiation of virtual machines that can be used by remote users to run mosaik-based co-simulations of complex energy systems employing their own simulation models, open-source software from the mosaik simulator pool, as well as systems from the SESA lab like the OPAL-RT eMEGAsim real-time simulation system.

6.2.6 RWTH: VLab

Access Provider: RWTH

Details: <https://erigrd2.eu/vlab/>

Description: RWTH provides a web-based simulation platform integrating existing simulation tools (see fig. 9) for providing Simulation-as-a-Service to a broader audience. This platform is built upon JupyterHub, a widespread open-source tool for interactive computing. The platform provides access to RWTH's dynamic phasor solver DPsim.

Figure 9: Screenshot of RWTH's Vlab.

6.2.7 UoS: Smartgrid MVP

Access Provider: UoS

Details: <https://erigrd2.eu/smartgrid-mvp/>

Description: Smartgrid MVP (formerly know as RT-Stream) of the Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory (DPSL) collects power systems measurement data from multiple data sources, including the Phasor Measurement Unit (PMU), within a single platform. This allows the data to be shared with other interested parties, in real-time (or near-real-time). Furthermore, historical recorded data (e.g., within a certain time range) will be available to access and download. Optionally, analysis can be performed locally on the data, such as correlation with other power system events and data sources.

6.2.8 HEDNO: RMO Database

Access Provider: HEDNO

Details: not yet online

Description: The VA facility *RMO Database* from HEDNO is currently being provisioned. A detailed description will be provided later.

6.2.9 DTU: Digital Energy Lab

Access Provider: DTU

Details: not yet online

Description: The VA facility *Digital Energy Lab* from DTU is currently being provisioned. A detailed description will be provided later.

6.3 User Support Forum

The ERIGrid 2.0 VA does not provide continuous support from on-site staff like the lab access scheme. Instead, the project provides support for the VA facilities via an online discussion forum (see Figure 10). This forum is hosted on RWTH's cloud infrastructure and accessible via the main project's domain¹³.

The support forum is provided by an open source discussion board named *Discourse*¹⁴ and deployed on a private *Kubernetes*¹⁵ cloud operated by the project partner RWTH.

¹³<https://forum.erigrd2.eu/>

¹⁴<https://discourse.org/>

¹⁵<https://kubernetes.io/>

Figure 10: Screenshot of the VA support forum.

6.4 User Questionnaire

For reporting purposes, users are diverted to a user questionnaire before being redirected to the web-address of the actual VA infrastructure. In the questionnaire users are asked to provide basic details about the intended use of the VA facility. The following information is collected:

- Company / Institution / University
- Type
- Country
- Email address
- Consent to participate for the evaluation of ERIGrid 2.0's VA programme (optional)

Figure 11 shows a screenshot of the questionnaire. The questionnaire is a custom implementation which is deployed on the same *Kubernetes* infrastructure as the support forum.

6.5 Single-sign on System

Some of the VA facilities require the users to register and authenticate themselves with a username/password. This is required for associating a user to its account, which includes for instance persistent project files or results on the provider's infrastructure. At the same time, user logins could be used to avoid abuse or misuse of the infrastructure.

ERIGrid 2.0 has decided to provide a common Identity Provider (IdP) for some of the VA facilities and the VA support forum. This single sign-on system is provided by the open-source identity management provider *Keycloak*¹⁶ and hosted on the server infrastructure of the partner AIT.

¹⁶<http://keycloak.org/>

ERIGrid 2.0 - Virtual Access

SmartEST Sim Lab

AIT's SmartEST Sim Lab is a simulation-as-a-service platform that is open to the public and can be used free of charge. It provides a web-based co-simulation platform based on mosaik, Docker, JupyterLab and JupyterHub.

- [Description](#)
- [Documentation](#)
- [Discussion Forum / FAQ](#)

Company / Institution / University

Type

Country

Email address

We'll never share your email with anyone else.

I consent to be contacted for the evaluation of ERIGrid's Virtual Access programme (optional).

[Access Installation](#)

Figure 11: Screenshot of the VA questionnaire.

6.6 Access Metrics and Statistics

As requested by the EC, the VA access provider must have the VA services assessed periodically by a board composed of international experts in the field.

Additionally, periodical technical reports must detail the access activity, with statistics on the VA provided in the period, including quantity, geographical distribution of users and, whenever possible, information/statistics on scientific outcomes (publications, patents, etc.) acknowledging the use of the infrastructure.

To provide inputs into the two types of reports, ERIGrid 2.0 has decided to implement the collection of web analytics for users visiting the VA facilities.

The collected statistics are augmented by the inputs provided by the users via the VA user questionnaire (see Section 6.4).

The web analytic services are provided by the open-source tool *Matomo*¹⁷ which is hosted by an external provider *Domaintechnik.at*¹⁸.

¹⁷<https://matomo.org/>

¹⁸<https://domaintechnik.at/>

7 Conclusions

The access activities program in ERIGrid 2.0 (i.e., lab access and VA services) is one of the main cornerstones in the realisation of the project. For a smooth and efficient implementation clear guidelines and rules are necessary. This report especially targets this point and provides a set of suggestions, procedures, and corresponding templates for the implementation of lab access activities as well as the usage of the provided VA services.

In view of the unprecedented general situation created by COVID-19 in 2020 which is also unexpectedly ongoing in the year 2021, several processes and routines in the project had to be adapted accordingly. Deviation management was handled with great composure and professionalism by the whole consortium. Especially for carrying out the work in the labs, the need to create virtual platforms and online space for co-operation became evident and thanks to the flexibility of all partners, in the area of lab access, this could be implemented with the enhanced roll-out of the VA opportunities. For the future, the consortium is striving to adhere to all requirements and time schedules according to the provisions of the grant agreement.

Future activities are mainly related to the screening and evaluation of the provided guidelines and their adaptations if it turns out that this is required.

References

Heussen, K., Steinbrink, C., Abdulhadi, I., Nguyen, V., Degefa, M., Merino, J., . . . Strasser, T. (2019). ERIGrid Holistic Test Description for Validating Cyber-Physical Energy Systems. *Energies*, 12(14), 2722.

Appendix A: Proposal Template

This appendix includes the proposal template to be filled by the UG applying for a lab access opportunity in the ERIGrid 2.0 calls. The source version can be downloaded from the ERIGrid 2.0 website¹⁹, where it can also be submitted electronically via the submission and reviewing system ConfTool²⁰.

¹⁹<https://erigrd2.eu/lab-access/>

²⁰<https://www.conftool.net/erigrd2/>

European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition

ERIGrid 2.0 LAB ACCESS APPLICATION FORM

USER PROJECT PROPOSAL

User Project Acronym	
User Project Title	
Main Scientific/Technical Field	
Proposal resubmitted (Y/N)	Choose an item.
Keywords (5 max., free text)	

PREFERRED HOST LABORATORY/RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Option 1	Choose an item.
Option 2	Choose an item.
Option 3	Choose an item.
Proposed starting date of the access	Click or tap to enter a date.
Expected access duration (in weeks)	

LEADER OF THE PROPOSING USER GROUP

Name	
Nationality	
Gender	Choose an item.
Age below 35-year-old (Y/N)?	Choose an item.
Email address	
Organization name	
Organization address	
Organization website	
Organization activity type	Choose an item.

MEMBERS OF THE PROPOSING USER GROUP (repeat for all Users)

Name	
Nationality	
Gender	Choose an item.
Age below 35-year-old (Y/N)?	Choose an item.
Email address	
Organization name	
Organization address	
Organization website	
Organization activity type	Choose an item.

[Please, fill the following sections taking into account that the final document should not be longer than 10 pages (i.e., applies for Points 1-9, excluding the meta data page(s); the italic/yellow text in the brackets should be removed; the rest will not be considered for the proposal evaluation). Please do not change the format and/or the font type/size of the template!]

European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition

1. SUMMARY OF PROPOSED RESEARCH (about ½ page)

[Prepare a ½ page summary describing the relevance, scope and objectives of the proposed work, and the expected outcomes.]

Text in 11 pt., Calibri

2. STATE-OF-THE-ART/RELATED WORK (about 1 ½ page)

[Describe in brief (about 1½ page) the current knowledge on the subject, citing recent relevant references. Identify any knowledge gaps and their relevance.]

Text in 11 pt., Calibri

3. DETAILED DESCRIPTION OF PROPOSED PROJECT: OBJECTIVES, EXPECTED OUTCOMES, AND FUNDAMENTAL SCIENTIFIC/TECHNICAL VALUE (3 pages maximum)

[Provide a detailed description of the objectives of the proposed activity, the way these objectives will be fulfilled through the proposed work, as well as indications on the expected outcomes and the fundamental scientific and technical value and interest of the proposal. Specify the activities to be undertaken, the type of infrastructure needed, the foreseen test setup, number of tests, possible test sequence, and parameters to be measured and controlled. Describe any special requirements for equipment, standards, safety measures, etc. Evaluate how robust and realistic the proposed approach is. Point out any shortcomings, uncertainties and risks for the fulfilment of the project objectives, as well as the means to mitigate relevant risks.]

Text in 11 pt., Calibri

4. ORIGINALITY, INNOVATION AND IMPACT OF PROPOSED RESEARCH (2 pages maximum)

[Demonstrate the originality and innovation of the proposed work and the impact the expected results will have on current and future research or practice, public safety, European standardization, competitiveness, integration and cohesion and on sustainable growth.]

Text in 11 pt., Calibri

5. SYNERGY WITH ONGOING RESEARCH (about ½ page)

[Provide information on any concurrent research project with the same or similar subject with the one proposed. Describe the synergy (if any) that will be sought between the existing and the proposed project. Explain the degree of alignment with the ERIGRID 2.0 approach, scope and objectives]

Text in 11 pt., Calibri

6. PROPOSED HOST LAB/RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE – JUSTIFICATION (about ½ page)

[Specify the type of infrastructure/installation needed for the research (e.g. microgrid, PHIL platform, etc.), which must be coherent with the preferred options indicated in the first page of this proposal; justifications should be provided on the grounds of the test setup, testing method, equipment, past experience in relevant subject, etc. Describe the potential benefits for the host research infrastructure in terms of improvement of know-how or enhancement of technologies and methods. Explain whether the proposing user group intends to deliver to the premises of the infrastructure parts or components to be tested at the user group's expense and responsibility, or to cover the whole or part of the construction/adaptation cost of the specimens to be tested.]

Text in 11 pt., Calibri

7. DISSEMINATION – EXPLOITATION OF RESULTS (about ½ page)

[In addition to the mandatory reporting for the access described in the "ERIGRID 2.0 Lab Access Guide" document, indicate other means through which the results to be obtained from the proposed project will be diffused and made broadly known.]

European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition

Text in 11 pt., Calibri

8. TIME SCHEDULE (about ½ page)

[Provide an indicative time-schedule for the proposed work and a target starting date.]

Text in 11 pt., Calibri

9. DESCRIPTION OF THE PROPOSING TEAM (1 pages maximum)

[Give a short description of each member (organization and persons) of the proposing team including projects, publications, technical experience and capabilities and role in the proposed project.]

Text in 11 pt., Calibri

Appendix B: Contract Model

A contract for the access to the lab between the proposing UG and the host lab must be signed by both parties before starting the project implementation for regulating the stay, lab use conditions and responsibilities of all parties involved. A reference model of this contract is included in this appendix containing the basic clauses; the host lab can include additional clauses in the final version to cover additional specific aspects of the stay, including country regulations and company-related conditions.

Addendum-A of the contract is the Technical Annex, which comprises the initial test case description to be implemented in the lab and the agreed work programme for performing the experiments during the access period. The final balance of 'access days' and 'stay days' of the UG members will be stated in the Addendum-B of the contract and signed by both parties at the end of the access.

CONTRACT MODEL

FOR USE BETWEEN THE USER GROUP AND THE ACCESS PROVIDER UNDER THE ERIGrid 2.0 LABORATORY ACCESS PROGRAMME

BY AND BETWEEN:

- (1) *<Access Provider name>* is a partner of the ERIGrid 2.0 project [Grant Agreement N° 870620], under the H2020 Research Programme [INFRAIA-2018-2020/H2020-INFRAIA-2019-1] (hereinafter “ACCESS PROVIDER”), and
- (2) The Home Institution of the User Group developing the PROJECT linked to the Proposal *<Proposal Acronym>* [*<Proposal Reference>*], beneficiary of the ERIGrid 2.0 Laboratory Access. The composition of the User Group (hereinafter “USER”) is stated in Addendum-C, where the User Group Leader is appointed.

Hereinafter may be referred to individually as a “Party” or collectively as the “Parties”.

This Contract is to enable the USER to get access to the INSTALLATION provided by the ACCESS PROVIDER to carry out a PROJECT assessed and approved during the ERIGrid 2.0 *<1st, 2nd, 3rd, ...>* Call for Lab Access Proposals.

USER	
Proposal Acronym	
Proposal Reference	
Name of the User Group Leader	
Home Institution of the User Group Leader:	
Name	
Address	
Country	

ACCESS PROVIDER	
Name of the ACCESS PROVIDER	
Name of the ACCESS PROVIDER representative	
INSTALLATION:	
Name	
Address	
Country	

The Parties agree the following:

1 Definitions

The Parties agree the following definitions:

- 1.1 **USER:** comprises all User Group members in accordance with Addendum-C having access to the INSTALLATION provided by the ACCESS PROVIDER.
- 1.2 **INSTALLATION:** group of instruments/devices being a part of a research infrastructure that can be used independently from the rest, and to which the USER has been awarded access by the ACCESS PROVIDER according to the Laboratory Access programme in ERIGrid 2.0.
- 1.3 **PROJECT:** research activities to be undertaken by the USER at the INSTALLATION according to the work programme annexed to this Contract ("Technical Annex").
- 1.4 **RESULTS:** means any tangible or intangible output of the PROJECT, such as inventions, works, data, knowledge or information that is generated in the PROJECT, whatever its form or nature, whether or not it can be protected, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights, industrial property rights and trade secrets.
- 1.5 **BACKGROUND:** means any inventions, works, data, know-how or information whatever its form or nature, tangible or intangible, including any rights such as intellectual property rights, industrial property rights and trade secrets, which is: (1) held by the Parties prior to the implementation of the PROJECT in the INSTALLATION, (2) needed for carrying out the PROJECT or for exploiting the RESULTS of the PROJECT, and (3) identified by the Parties.
- 1.6 **ACCESS DAY:** day spent by the USER at the INSTALLATION performing the research activities of the PROJECT. This includes also the additional days dedicated by the ACCESS PROVIDER to prepare the INSTALLATION for the PROJECT (set-up of the experiments in the laboratory).
- 1.7 **STAY DAY:** day spent by the USER performing the PROJECT in the country where the INSTALLATION is located; it includes the ACCESS DAYS in the INSTALLATION, working days at the ACCESS PROVIDER's office¹, and weekend days if applicable.

2 Access Provision

- 2.1 **Access Responsible Person (ARP):** the ACCESS PROVIDER shall nominate an ARP for the PROJECT which will be performed by the USER at the INSTALLATION. The ARP shall be in charge of supervising the experimental activity at the INSTALLATION (including the safety matters), and supporting the USER in all technical, administrative and logistic needs. During the PROJECT, when an issue dictates the need for support request by the USER, the first point of contact should always be the ARP.
- 2.2 The ACCESS PROVIDER agrees to provide access to the INSTALLATION as needed for the PROJECT as follows:

INSTALLATION name	
Start → End date	.../.../... → .../.../...
N° of Access Days	

¹ Normally, in addition to the effective work at the INSTALLATION, the USER will carry out some tasks at the ACCESS PROVIDER premises (not at the INSTALLATION but in the office): preparation of the experiments, analysis and processing of intermediate results, etc.

Parties acknowledge the above schedule. In case of schedule modifications, the ACCESS PROVIDER must inform the USER within five (5) days notice minimum.

Once the access to the INSTALLATION is finished, the USER and the ACCESS PROVIDER must declare the final use in terms of “access days” and “stay days”, in accordance with the standard Form of Addendum-B.

- 2.3 Before and after the USER access, the ARP and the USER check together the functioning conditions of the INSTALLATION for the scope of the PROJECT. Possible malfunctions are reported in a specific Report countersigned by both Parties.

3 General Obligations of the Parties

- 3.1 Notwithstanding Clause 13 of this Contract (“Governing Law” Clause), the Parties shall each abide by their own respective national laws and regulations including, but not limited to, laws and/or regulations which govern employment, immigration, taxation, social security, personal and public liability, data protection and insurance.
- 3.2 The Parties shall act in good faith to resolve any dispute, controversy or claim (the “Matter”) via referral of the Matter to its senior management representative for dispute resolution between the Parties concerned. Where the Matter has not been resolved to the reasonable satisfaction of the Parties concerned within forty five (45) days or a longer period mutually agreed between the Parties concerned, the Parties shall refer the Matter for resolution in accordance with Clause 13 of this Contract. This provision does not restrict the possibility of applying for interim injunction.
- 3.3 Except as expressly provided for in this Contract, none of the terms and conditions herein shall be enforceable by a third party.

4 Rights, Obligations and Responsibilities

- 4.1 The USER Home Institution ensures that the USER fulfils its obligation set out in this contract and is responsible to the ACCESS PROVIDER for this.
- 4.2 The USER or its Home Institution must have the appropriate insurances to cover all members of the User Group during the stay period. This includes:
- Medical insurance.
 - Travel insurance (accidents during travels made for work purposes and accidents on the way to work and back from work).
 - General Liability insurance.

The foregoing shall be without prejudice to the additional insurance requirements or specifications that may be laid down by the ACCESS PROVIDER.

- 4.3 The USER or its Home Institution are responsible for obtaining any work permits, residence permits, visas or other documents necessary for the stay.
- 4.4 The USER or its Home Institution are responsible for obtaining accommodation in the place of the stay.
- 4.5 Where required and in a timely manner prior to the start date of the PROJECT, the USER or its Home Institution have to provide reasonable information and/or assistance to the ACCESS PROVIDER in order to abide by its own internal procedures or those of its national authority.

- 4.6 The USER must at all times follow all ACCESS PROVIDER's security and safety requirements and instructions.
- 4.7 The USER is responsible to behave always in a manner that is ethical, legal and not to the detriment of others.
- 4.8 The USER must act in such a manner as not to cause damage to the physical equipment or premises of the ACCESS PROVIDER. Any damage caused by the USER or third parties, must be reported to the ARP as soon as possible so that corrective actions can be taken and further damages or negative consequences can be avoided or minimised.
- 4.9 The USER is responsible for protecting their own files and data from reading and/or writing by others.
- 4.10 The USER has the right not be harassed while using the INSTALLATION, whether it is physical, verbal, electronic, or any other form of abuse. Harassment should be reported immediately to the ARP.
- 4.11 The USER must enjoy a reasonable standard of care in relation to health and safety at the INSTALLATION, similar to the ACCESS PROVIDER's staff holding a similar position.
- 4.12 The USER must not develop or use programs to bypass system security mechanisms, harm the system, steal passwords or data, evade software licensing or copyright restrictions, or replicate themselves (viruses, worms, etc.).
- 4.13 No software is to be downloaded and/or installed onto any of the INSTALLATION machines without the explicit and written consent of the ARP; this includes, but is not limited to, applications, utilities, fonts, games, and web browser plug-ins. If the USER needs software to be installed onto the INSTALLATION machines, he must submit a written request to the ARP; all requests will be reviewed for cost, licensing restrictions, and security aspects. Installing software that violates licence agreement and copyright laws is strictly prohibited.
- 4.14 Software in use on the ACCESS PROVIDER's facilities, unless it is stored in areas specifically marked as containing software available for copying, must not be copied to external disks, pen drives, including any other media, or otherwise removed from the facilities. Copyrighted or licensed software must not be copied whole or in part.
- 4.15 Under no circumstances may the USER alter a file that does not belong to him or her without prior written permission of the file owner. Files owned by the USER are to be considered as private property, whether they are accessible to others or not.
- 4.16 ACCESS PROVIDER's facilities and network connections must not be used for the purpose of making unauthorised connections to, breaking into, or adversely affecting the performance of other systems on the network, whether these systems and network are owned by the ACCESS PROVIDER or not.
- 4.17 The USER must get notice in advance about planned system shutdowns for maintenance, upgrades or changes. Efforts must be made by the ACCESS PROVIDER to give the USER a chance to save its work before the system is taken out of service. However, in the event of an emergency, the ACCESS PROVIDER may shut down systems with little or no advance notification.

5 Liability

- 5.1 The ACCESS PROVIDER is not liable for any use of the RESULTS generated in the PROJECT. In the event of Third Party claims for compensation against the ACCESS PROVIDER arising from the USER Home Institution's exploitation of PROJECT RESULTS (including but not limited to claims based on product liability regulations), the USER Home Institution shall – notwithstanding anything to the contrary set out herein – defend and hold the ACCESS PROVIDER harmless from such claims.
- 5.2 In case of unavailability of the INSTALLATION, the ACCESS PROVIDER cannot be held responsible. Under no circumstances, can the USER obtain any compensatory damages.
- 5.3 In agreeing on access to the INSTALLATION, each Party acknowledges that due to the intrinsic nature of research, specific results or outcomes cannot be guaranteed when carrying out the experimental research, and therefore, the ACCESS PROVIDER will not be responsible of any associated delays in the PROJECT. However, this shall not apply in the event of wilful misconduct.
- 5.4 Except in the case of a wilful act, gross negligence or breach of confidentiality, no Party shall be responsible to the other Party for any indirect or consequential loss or damages such as, but not limited to, loss of profit, loss of revenue or loss of contracts howsoever caused.
- 5.5 Each Party shall be solely liable for any loss, damage or injury caused to any third parties resulting from the performance of said Party's obligations under this Contract or under the PROJECT.

6 Intellectual Property Rights

- 6.1 The USER must obtain written permission from the owner of any BACKGROUND before using it in the PROJECT and must comply with any conditions set by the owner. Ownership of BACKGROUND will remain unchanged by this Contract.
- 6.2 The ACCESS PROVIDER will, on request from the USER, and where it is free to do so, make available for non-commercial use on a royalty-free basis, any own BACKGROUND which is reasonably needed for the PROJECT, unless this is contrary to the own interests of the ACCESS PROVIDER. This can include, for example, economic or academic interests.
- 6.3 RESULTS generated during the PROJECT will be owned by the Parties which generate it.
- 6.4 Where RESULTS, which have been generated jointly and inseparably between the USER and the ACCESS PROVIDER as a result of their collaborative efforts and it is impossible to ascertain individual shares based on their respective intellectual contributions, then such jointly developed RESULTS shall be jointly owned by the USER and the ACCESS PROVIDER ("Jointly Owned RESULTS" and "Joint Owners" respectively). The Joint Owners shall establish a separate Agreement in writing regarding the allocation, protection measures and terms of exercising such Jointly Owned RESULTS on fair and reasonable terms and shall take into account the contributions to the PROJECT made by each of the Joint Owners.
- 6.5 Where no joint ownership agreement has yet been concluded between the Joint Owners of the Jointly Owned RESULTS pursuant to Clause 6.4 then the Joint Owners hereby agree that the following terms shall apply:
 - a) Each of the Joint Owners shall be entitled to grant non-exclusive licenses to Third Parties (excluding the right to sub-license) to and commercially use their Jointly Owned RESULTS and without requiring the prior consent of the other Joint Owner/s subject to the following conditions:

- At least forty five (45) days prior written notice must be given to the other Joint Owner/s and

- Fair and reasonable compensation must be provided to the other Joint Owner/s

b) The Joint Owners shall agree on all protection measures and the division of related cost in advance of 6.5.a) above.

6.6 Each of the Joint Owners shall be entitled to use the Jointly Owned RESULTS solely for non-commercial research and development purposes on a royalty-free, non-exclusive, non-transferable basis as long as the protection of such Jointly Owned RESULTS is not adversely affected. Such non-commercial research shall include research projects with third parties within the limitations as set out in this Clause 6.6.

7 Confidentiality

7.1 Subject to the provisions set out herein, both Parties will keep confidential any Confidential Information (as defined below) communicated or disclosed to them by the other Party in connection with this Contract.

7.2 Exchange of Confidential Information will be on a bilateral basis between the USER and the ACCESS PROVIDER.

7.3 Notwithstanding anything to the contrary set out herein, any BACKGROUND or RESULTS owned by the ACCESS PROVIDER shall be treated as Confidential Information by the USER, in line with this Article.

7.4 The Confidential Information of the USER shall (where possible) be destroyed, diced or otherwise made invisible and unavailable to any other party, unless otherwise specified on a case by case basis. If destroyed, such destruction shall be guaranteed in writing.

7.5 Each Party's acceptance and use of Confidential Information shall be subject to the following:

a) For purposes of this Contract, "Confidential Information" means any and all non-public and/or proprietary information and/or data in any form and of any nature whatsoever -including, but not limited to, all written or printed documents, samples, models, and/or information whether or not patentable- disclosed by either Party ("Provider") to the other Party ("Recipient") in connection with this Contract, whether disclosed in oral, written, graphic, machine recognizable (including computer programs or data bases), model or sample form, or any derivation thereof. Confidential Information, if in written or other tangible form, must be marked or designated in writing by the Provider with a notice indicating its proprietary nature, and if in oral form or visual form, must be summarized in writing and delivered to the Recipient within thirty (30) days from the disclosure of such Confidential Information

b) Prior to disclosure, the Provider shall inform the Recipient of the nature and general content of the Confidential Information which is forthcoming. The Recipient may refuse the acceptance of Confidential Information prior to its disclosure. If refused Confidential Information is sent to the refusing Party nevertheless, the refusing Party will inform the Provider, destroy the Confidential Information in question as soon as he realizes the confidentiality of the information. Nevertheless, the Recipient is not obliged to maintain confidentiality with regard to this information.

- c) The Recipient shall use no less than the same degree of care it uses for its own Confidential Information (and in any event, reasonable standard care), and not publish or otherwise reveal the Confidential Information to its personnel not involved in the PROJECT or to individuals outside its organization without the prior written permission of the Provider. Confidential Information shall only be disclosed to the Recipient's own employees who have a reasonable need-to-know the Confidential Information within the frame of the PROJECT and who shall be bound by confidentiality obligations at least as stringent as the one provided for in this Article.
- d) The Recipient shall not copy, disassemble, reverse engineer or decompile the Confidential Information without prior written consent of Provider. Any such copies shall be identified as belonging to Provider and prominently marked "Confidential".
- e) The Recipient shall not disclose another Party's Confidential Information to any Third Party without the prior written consent by the Disclosing Party. This does not apply where Confidential Information has to be provided to the European Commission under the PROJECT or in connection with this Contract (see e.g. Clause 9).
- f) The obligations of this Clause 7 do not apply if and as far as the Recipient can prove that the Confidential Information:
- Is already in the public domain or becomes available to the public through no breach of this Contract by the Recipient; or
 - Was in the Recipient's possession prior to the receipt from the Provider; or
 - Is received by the Recipient from a third party without any confidentiality obligations; or
 - Is subsequently and completely independent from the receipt of the Confidential Information developed by Recipient; or
 - Is required to be disclosed by the Recipient pursuant to any order or requirement of a Court, Administrative Agency, or any other Governmental Agency, provided that the Recipient shall, to the extent it is lawfully able to do so, give the Provider prompt written notice of such order or requirement prior to disclosure, allow the Provider to contest or seek an appropriate protective order, and comply with the Provider's reasonable instructions to protect the confidentiality of the Confidential Information.
- g) Confidential Information shall remain the property of the Provider and shall, where practically and legally possible, be destroyed or returned to the Provider along with all copies thereof upon termination or expiration of the Contract. If destroyed, such destruction shall be guaranteed in writing.
- h) The Recipient shall promptly advise the Provider in writing of any unauthorized disclosure, misappropriation or misuse of confidential information after it becomes aware of such unauthorized disclosure, misappropriation or misuse.
- i) The confidentiality obligation with respect to any Confidential Information shall remain in force for a period of five (5) years from the date of expiration of termination of the Contract. Concerning Confidential Information which cannot be destroyed (i.e. backup copies) the Recipient shall refrain to use such Confidential Information, and the confidentiality and non-use obligation shall continue until such Confidential Information is destroyed.

8 Safety Provisions

- 8.1 The ACCESS PROVIDER will take reasonable care to ensure the safety of the USER during their access to the INSTALLATION, in compliance with all relevant and prevailing regulations such as Health, Safety and Security Regulations. It cannot be held liable for death or injury to Users caused through their own negligence.

- 8.2 The ACCESS PROVIDER should coordinate general preventive actions defined by the Law of *<Country of Installation>*.
- 8.3 The USER will follow the safety instructions and procedures of the INSTALLATION to be used for the PROJECT and for the ACCESS PROVIDER's premises in general. The USER will adhere to all hazard control requirements specified for the INSTALLATION. This also applies the COVID-19 measures: wearing face masks, keeping protection distances, following sanitizing instructions, etc.
- 8.4 The USER must be informed about the emergency equipment and procedures, escape route, rescue plan and special dangers in the ACCESS PROVIDER's facilities. It is upon the ACCESS PROVIDER to make the USER sign a declaration document to confirm that they have received and agreed the necessary safety and security instructions.
- 8.5 For safety reasons the USER is not expected to operate the INSTALLATION by himself; even when safety instructions will be provided, tests will be carried out by staff of the ACCESS PROVIDER.
- 8.6 The USER must not use the INSTALLATION without written permission from the ARP. The USER must not use the INSTALLATION without the presence of the ARP or her/his delegate.
- 8.7 Before beginning any experiment at the INSTALLATION, a safety review must be conducted to consider potential hazards of the set-up and the experimental procedure, so as to follow the appropriate safety precautions.
- 8.8 During the PROJECT experiments, working areas must be kept clean and free from obstacles. Clean-up should follow the completion of any experiment.
- 8.9 If applicable, the USER will carry his own proper protective clothing and equipment and wear them for the experiments of the PROJECT.
- 8.10 Unless otherwise agreed, food and drink (including water) are not to be brought into the INSTALLATION at any time. Eating, drinking and smoking are not allowed at the INSTALLATION.
- 8.11 The USER must use the INSTALLATION in accordance with the supplier User Guide/s or the INSTALLATION User Manual/s (if any). The USER will read the Safety Data Sheet (if any) before using the INSTALLATION.
- 8.12 The USER must be alert to known unsafe conditions and call attention to them so corrections can be made as soon as possible. The USER will report any accident, injury, dangerous situation, or unusual occurrence immediately to the ARP or delegates, and will follow the corresponding instructions.
- 8.13 The USER acknowledges that the INSTALLATION must be operative when given it back. The USER undertakes in faith to let the ARP known of any malfunctions the USER might encounter during the use of the INSTALLATION.
- 8.14 In case of direct involvement of the USER in activities related to potential personnel risks (i.e. components/instrumentation installation and set-up), the USER must prepare, and send in advance to the ACCESS PROVIDER for approval, a Safety Plan for the foreseen activities that includes risk assessment (evaluation of potential risks, potential cases and prevention measures) and a list of personnel involved in the activities (who will be the only allowed to perform them).

9 Reporting

9.1 The ACCESS PROVIDER has the obligation to keep the Commission informed about the use being made of the INSTALLATION.

9.2 The USER will:

- a) Report to the ACCESS PROVIDER on the progress of the work when required by the ARP for the PROJECT.
- b) Fill the European Commission's on-line questionnaire providing feedback about the access and the stay at the ACCESS PROVIDER's facilities:

<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS>

This tool is used by the Commission to evaluate the Research Infrastructures Action and monitor the ERIGrid 2.0 Grant Agreement.

- c) Prepare a detailed Technical Report, describing the objectives and experiments, and comprising the obtained results and conclusions. This document must contain an Executive Summary (2 pages maximum).
 - d) Inform the ACCESS PROVIDER of any publication or presentation made on the work of the PROJECT to provide evidence of the soundness of the scientific work performed at the ACCESS PROVIDER's INSTALLATION under this opportunity. Any publication or presentation shall be sent to the ACCESS PROVIDER at least 45 calendar days before publication. The ACCESS PROVIDER may raise justified objections to the planned publication (e.g. an objection is justified if the protection of the objecting Party's RESULTS or BACKGROUND would be adversely affected or, the objecting Party's legitimate interests in relation to the RESULTS or BACKGROUND would be significantly harmed). Any justified objection of the ACCESS PROVIDER shall be made within 30 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made the publication is permitted. Furthermore, this information may be used by the ACCESS PROVIDER in its reports to the Commission.
 - e) Note that ERIGrid 2.0 reports to the European Commission will contain the names, home institutions and description of the work of the USER. The ERIGrid 2.0 website will publish a list of projects naming the researchers' organizations, research project titles and short descriptions, and the facilities used. The USER must also note that the European Commission has the right to publish the list of users. Therefore, in signing this Contract the USER Home Institution guarantees that the USER agrees to the use of such data as described herein. Should the description of the work provided include any personal data, the USER Home Institution shall ensure that it has a legitimate right to disclose such personal data to the use as described herein.
- 9.3 The USER will fill the on-line EC questionnaire (9.2.b) and submit the Technical Report (9.2.c) to the ERIGrid 2.0 Lab Access Manager within two (2) months after the end of the stay.
- 9.4 USER's publications mentioned in "9.2.d)" must:
- a) Be in English (at least the first one associated to the access).
 - b) Display the EU emblem.
 - c) Indicate that they reflect only the author's view and that the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information they contain.

d) Include the following acknowledgement:

“This research has been performed using the ERIGrid 2.0 Research Infrastructure and is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under the Grant Agreement No. 870620. The support of the European Research Infrastructure ERIGrid 2.0 and its partner <name> is very much appreciated”.

10 Access Expenses

10.1 The lab access offered by ERIGrid 2.0 covers the USER’s expenses for travel and subsistence according to the H2020 rules and the ACCESS PROVIDER conditions².

10.2 No other costs (other than eligible travel and subsistence costs) may be claimed by the USER or the USER Home Institution pursuant to the PROJECT.

10.3 The ACCESS PROVIDER will:

- a) Provide free access to the INSTALLATION and assist the USER in the use of the INSTALLATION as specified in this Contract.
- b) Reimburse eligible travel and subsistence expenditures of the USER, which are reasonably and properly incurred during the access period in relation to the PROJECT. The ACCESS PROVIDER may retain the reimbursement of the 30% of the USER’s expenses until the completion of the mandatory reporting by the USER (clauses 9.2.b and 9.2.c).

10.4 The USER and its Home Institution:

- a) Agrees to maintain detailed records relating to its travel and subsistence expenses claims and shall submit to the ACCESS PROVIDER for approval the corresponding invoices/receipts when the access is finished³. As an alternative for the subsistence expense coverage, each member of the USER can receive a daily grant of XXX.YY EURO/day as a lump sum covering all expenses for subsistence during the stay at the ACCESS PROVIDER’s facilities; in this case, the USER will sign the corresponding receipt during the access.
- b) Agrees to submit to the ACCESS PROVIDER only those claims for travel and subsistence expenses which have been legitimately incurred in connection with the PROJECT.
- c) Acknowledges and agrees that its travel and subsistence claims may be onward disclosed by the ACCESS PROVIDER to the European Commission for the purpose of a financial audit.
- d) Acknowledges that the European Commission may require specific proof of travel expenditure in the form of original receipts.
- e) Will make reasonable travel and daily subsistence expenses: low-cost company, economy class and public transportation, whenever possible, accommodation in conventional (not luxurious) hotels or equivalent lodging, and meals in regular restaurants.

10.5 The ERIGrid 2.0 lab access scheme does not fund the research involved in the PROJECT

² The concrete access conditions applicable to the individual installations can be found at the ERIGrid 2.0 website: www.erigrd2.eu.

³ For the declaration of the incurred expenses a template will be made available by the ACCESS PROVIDER. Normally, the ACCESS PROVIDER will indicate a reference maximum amount per person for the daily subsistence fee as an indication for the users.

(e.g. the researchers wages), only the mentioned associated travel and subsistence expenses.

- 10.6 The USER and its Home Institution shall be solely liable for justifying any travel and subsistence claims to the European Commission. In the event that the European Commission demands the return of any over-payment made to the USER where a claim (or part of a claim) has been deemed to be an ineligible cost, the USER and its Home Institution shall be solely responsible for re-funding of any such payment immediately to the ACCESS PROVIDER upon written demand. The USER and its Home Institution agrees to keep the ACCESS PROVIDER fully indemnified against any and all claims or refunds that the ACCESS PROVIDER is required to make to the European Commission on behalf of the USER.

11 European Commission Verification

- 11.1 The USER and its Home Institution acknowledge that the Commission has the right to carry out a technical verification of the PROJECT and that this may involve a site visit during which documents are accessed and progress assessed. The USER and its Home Institution agree to cooperate in such an audit and acknowledges the Commission's commitment to treating technical information in confidence.

12 Implementation and Termination

- 12.1 Notwithstanding the date of execution hereof which shall occur on the later date of signature between the Parties, this Contract shall have effect as from *<insert date>* (the "Effective Date") and shall remain in full force and effect for the access period.
- 12.2 The access period for implementing the PROJECT in the INSTALLATION shall be allocated to a date within the next six (6) months after the acceptance notification to the USER.
- 12.3 Due to the COVID-19 pandemic (or a similar exceptional situation), a reasonable flexibility shall be shown by the ACCESS PROVIDER regarding the access period and other involved organizational aspects.
- 12.4 Expiry period: this Contract can be terminated by the ACCESS PROVIDER if the user PROJECT has not been implemented in the INSTALLATION within the next three (3) months after the Contract comes into force, and no notification or explanation has been provided by the USER or its Home Institution and accepted by the ACCESS PROVIDER.
- 12.5 If there is a conflict between this Contract and the Grant Agreement N° 870620, then the latter shall take precedence.
- 12.6 No modification shall be made to this Contract except with the prior written consent of the Parties which shall be made by amendment to this Contract by duly authorised signatories of the Parties.
- 12.7 Should any provision of this Contract become invalid, illegal or unenforceable, it shall not affect the validity of the remaining provisions of this Contract which shall continue in force notwithstanding such severance. In such a case, the Parties concerned shall be entitled to demand that a valid and practicable provision be negotiated which mostly fulfils the purpose of the invalid, illegal or unenforceable provision.
- 12.8 Either Party may terminate this Contract at one (1) month's written notice for major technical or economic reasons affecting the PROJECT.
- 12.9 Those provisions of this Contract which by their nature or implication are required to survive expiry or termination of this Contract shall so survive and continue in full force and effect,

together with any other provisions of this Contract necessary to give effect to such provisions.

13 Governing Law and Dispute Resolution

- 13.1 This contract is governed by the law of *<Country of ACCESS PROVIDER>*.
- 13.2 Nothing in this Contract shall be deemed to require a Party to breach or violate any mandatory national laws or regulations in the country where a Party is operating.
- 13.3 All disputes arising out of or in connection with this Contract, which cannot be solved amicably, shall be submitted to the *<courts of ...>*.

SIGNATURES

We agree to conduct the PROJECT in the manner described in this document. IN WITNESS WHEREOF, the undersigned have signed the present Contract.

For and on behalf of the USER Home Institution <i><name of USER Home Institution></i>	For and on behalf of <i><Access Provider name></i>
<i><Signature of the Authorized Representative of the USER Home Institution></i>	<i><Signature of the ACCESS PROVIDER representative></i>
Name:	Name:
Title:	Title:
Date:	Date:

Addendum-A: Technical Annex

This Addendum must contain the Technical Annex that describes the Test Case and the work programme (tasks, experiment plan, time schedule, etc.) of the PROJECT to be performed during the access period in the INSTALLATION. This Technical Annex must be coherent with the proposal approved by the User Selection Panel according to the established criteria (even though some adjustments in practice can be introduced if agreed between the USER and the ACCESS PROVIDER).

Please note that significant modifications of the technical content or the access conditions (e.g., number of access days) with respect to the planned ones in the proposal should be checked with the ERIGrid 2.0 Lab Access Manager and the ERIGrid 2.0 Coordinator for approval, before the access can take place.

For the formulation of the Test Case the HTD canvas must be used to facilitate the realisation of complex and repeatable experiments. This tool frames the purpose of the experiment, and identifies relevant functions, structures and components; by combining narrative, with graphical, qualitative, structured and quantitative/formal elements, domain specifics are given a shared testing context. For complex experiments, it is advisable to formulate it with detail; for simpler experiments it is sufficient to clarify Test Objective, Purpose of Investigation and System under Test.

*[Please insert the Technical Annex here:
 (1) work programme
 (2) test case description: use the following HTD canvas]*

TITLE:		AUTHOR: DATE:
Object under Investigation (Q_{UI}) "The component(s) (L _{u,n}) that are to be qualified by the test"	Test Objectives Why is the test needed? What do we expect to find out?	System under Test (S_{UT}) Systems, subsystems, components included in the test case or test setup
Function(s) under Investigation (F_{UI}) "The referenced specification of a function realized (operationalized) by the object under investigation"		Purpose of Investigation (P_{UI}) The test purposes classified in with terms <i>Characterization, Verification, or Validation</i>
Domain under Investigation (D_{UI}): "The relevant domains of test parameters and connectivity"	Test criteria (TCR) Formulation of criteria for each P _{UI} based on properties of S _{UT} ; encompasses properties of test signals and output measures	Variability attributes (VA) Identify relevant controllable or uncontrollable factors of the S _{UT} and their required variability; refer to P _{UI} .
Target metrics (TM) Measures retrievable from S _{UT} , required to quantify each of the identified test criteria	Quality attributes (QA) Threshold levels for test result quality as well as pass/fail criteria	

Addendum-B: Declaration of Use of ERIGrid 2.0 Infrastructure

After the stay and when the access to the INSTALLATION is finished, the USER and the ACCESS PROVIDER must declare the final use in terms of “access days” and “stay days”, in accordance with the following template.

DECLARATION OF USE OF ERIGrid 2.0 INFRASTRUCTURE

Identification of the User Project (Acronym)	
Name of the User Group Leader	
Home Institution of the User Group Leader	
Name of the INSTALLATION	
ACCESS PROVIDER	

We declare that the INSTALLATION has been used according to the following figures:

Name of User	User Nationality	Home Institution and Country	Start → End date	N° of Stay Days	N° of Access Days
			DD/MM/YYYY → D/MM/YYYY		
			DD/MM/YYYY → D/MM/YYYY		
Total access provided^(*)			DD/MM/YYYY → D/MM/YYYY		

(*) If not all the users have been at the host installation on the same days, indicate in this row the overall access figures: first and last day of the stay (with at least one of the users), number of access days when at least one user was implementing the project in the installation, and number of stay days associated to the stay period (with the presence of at least one user).

In the name of the User Group <User Home Institution>	In the name of <Access Provider name>
<Signature of the User Group Leader>	<Signature of the ACCESS PROVIDER representative>
Name:	Name:
Title:	Title:
Date: DD/MM/YYYY	Date: DD/MM/YYYY

Addendum-C: User Group Leader appointment by User Group Members

Lab Access Call N°	
User Project Acronym:	
User Project Title:	

Declaration of User Group members:

We hereby confirm that *<...name of the Leader...>* is the User Group Leader for the *<...acronym of the user project...>* project to be implemented through the Laboratory Access Programme of ERIGrid 2.0.

User Group members:

<i><...name of the Leader...></i>	<i><...signature of the Leader...></i>
<i><...name of member1...></i>	<i><...signature of member1...></i>
<i><...name of member2...></i>	<i><...signature of member2...></i>
...	...

Appendix C: EC Questionnaire

This questionnaire is provided online at the corresponding EC website²¹.

EUSURVEY

European Commission > EUSurvey

Save a backup on your local computer (disable if you are using a public/shared computer)

Research Infrastructures: User group questionnaire

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

Research Infrastructures: User group questionnaire

One of the aims of the [European Commission Research Infrastructures Action](#) is to provide scientists from anywhere within the Union with easy access to Europe's major research infrastructures. The Action is implemented through grant agreements between the European Commission and network of key European research infrastructures. These grant agreements serve to support, among others, the mobility costs of visiting scientists and their costs of using the infrastructure.

To enable the Commission to evaluate the Research Infrastructures Action, to monitor the individual grant agreements, and to improve the services provided to the scientific community, each Group Leader of a user-project supported under an EU Research Infrastructure grant agreement is requested to complete the present "User Group Questionnaire". The questionnaire must be submitted once by each user group as soon as the experiments on the infrastructure come to end.

All replies will be treated in strictest confidence. The information given will only be used for monitoring and assessment purposes.

User group questionnaire

*
1. Number and Acronym of the EC Grant Agreement that supported the user group's access to the research infrastructure(s) (please check [here](#))

*
2. User Project Acronym (Please indicate the acronym of the user's project you are involved in, as assigned by your host infrastructure)

*
3. Person filling in the questionnaire (normally the User Group Leader)

Family name

*
First name(s)

*
4. Where did you first find out about the possibilities of access supported through the EC grant agreement?

- EC Research Infrastructures Action web-site
- Grant Agreement web-site
- Infrastructure web-site
- Announcement in Journal
- Announcement at conference
- Direct mailing from infrastructure
- National Contact Point (NCP)
- Personal contact

If by personal contact (please specify)

*
5. Without the support of this EC grant agreement would you still have been able to carry out your work at this research infrastructure?

Yes
 No

If no, please indicate the reason (you may indicate more than one choice)

Views
Standard [Accessibility Mode](#)

Languages
[EN] English ▾

Contact
RTD-RI-MAP@ec.europa.eu

[Download PDF version](#)

[Report abuse](#)

²¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS>

Appendix D: Expenses Declaration Form

When the access is completed, the UG can use the following form for declaring the incurred expenses during the access. The sheet must be signed by the UG members and the bank account details provided to get the refund. This declaration must be accompanied with a copy of the corresponding invoices and tickets (scanned file) and sent to the host infrastructure for approval and refund.

H2020 ERIGrid 2.0 Project (870620)

ERIGrid 2.0 Hosting Lab/Research Infrastructure

**ERIGrid 2.0 LAB ACCESS
INVOICE / EXPENSE SHEET**

When filled in and signed, please send your scanned invoice together with all other reports to the hosting institution for further processing

< Official Name of Hosting Institution > < Name of department/institute/unit/group (optiona)> att. < Name of the contact person of the host > < Address line one, e.g., street name, street number > < Address line two, e.g., postal code city, country >	DATE: 21 December 2020
--	------------------------

Lab Access User Group Information

USER GROUP LEADER	< First Name, Last Name >
USER GROUP ORGANIZATION	< Official Name of Organization >
EMAIL ADDRESS	< Contact Email Address >
POSTAL ADDRESS	< Address line one, e.g., street name, street number > < Address line two, e.g., postal code city, country >
PHONE NUMBER	< Contact Phone Number >
VAT REGISTRATION NUMBER *	

Lab Access Project Information

PROJECT ACRONYM	< Project Acronym >
PROJECT REFERENCE	< Project Number from the submission system, e.g., 100 >
PERIOD OF STAY	< dd/mm/yyyy - dd/mm/yyyy >
NUMBER OF STAY DAYS	< dd >
NUMBER OF ACCESS DAYS	< dd >

EXPENSES

#	Description	Dates	Net Sum (€) (without VAT)	Sum (€)	Document
1	< Plane ticket >	dd/mm/yyyy - dd/mm/yyyy	0.00	0.00	< Invoice n° ... >
2	< Hotel xxx >	dd/mm/yyyy - dd/mm/yyyy	0.00	0.00	< PDF file (scanned tickets) >
3	< Public transport xxx >	dd/mm/yyyy - dd/mm/yyyy	0.00	0.00	< ... >
4	< ... >	dd/mm/yyyy - dd/mm/yyyy	0.00	0.00	< ... >
5	< ... >	dd/mm/yyyy - dd/mm/yyyy	0.00	0.00	< ... >
...	< ... >	dd/mm/yyyy - dd/mm/yyyy	0.00	0.00	< ... >
Total €			-	€ -	

Lab Access User Group Signatures

USER GROUP MEMBER'S SIGNATURES	< Signature 1 >	< Signature 2 >	< Signature 3 >	< Signature 4 >
INSTITUTION'S STAMP *	< Fist Name, Last Name >			

Bank Details for Reimbursement

NAME OF THE BANK	
SUBJECT/COMMENT	
ADDRESS OF THE BANK	
ACCOUNT HOLDER NAME	
IBAN ACCOUNT NUMBER	
BIC (SWIFT) CODE	

* If non applicable, leave it blank.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 870620.

Consortium

Disclaimer

All information provided reflects the status of the ERIGrid 2.0 project at the time of writing and may be subject to change.

Neither the ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium as a whole, nor any single party within the ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium warrant that the information contained in this document is capable of use, nor that the use of such information is free from risk. Neither the ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium as a whole, nor any single party within the ERIGrid 2.0 Consortium accepts any liability for loss or damage suffered by any person using the information.

This document does not represent the opinion of the European Community, and the European Community is not responsible for any use that might be made of its content.

Copyright Notice

© 2021 by the authors, the ERIGrid 2.0 consortium. This work is licensed under a "CC BY 4.0" license.

